

Data Availability statement

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Table 1: Search strategy for included studies

<p>MEDLINE via PubMed</p>	<p>((("Renal Dialysis"[Mesh]) AND "Erythropoietin"[Mesh]) AND "Mortality"[Mesh]) OR (((("Dialyses, Renal"[Title/Abstract] OR "Renal Dialyses"[Title/Abstract] OR "Dialysis, Renal"[Title/Abstract] OR Hemodialysis[Title/Abstract] OR Hemodialyses[Title/Abstract] OR "Dialysis, Extracorporeal"[Title/Abstract] OR "Dialyses, Extracorporeal"[Title/Abstract] OR "Extracorporeal Dialyses"[Title/Abstract] OR "Extracorporeal Dialysis"[Title/Abstract]) AND (erythropoietin[Title/Abstract] OR "Epoetin Alfa"[Title/Abstract] OR "Erythropoiesis stimulating agent"[Title/Abstract] OR "Darbepoetin alfa"[Title/Abstract] OR epex[Title/Abstract])) AND (mortality[Title/Abstract] OR Mortalities[Title/Abstract] OR "Case Fatality Rate"[Title/Abstract] OR "Case Fatality Rates"[Title/Abstract] OR "Rate, Case Fatality"[Title/Abstract] OR "Rates, Case Fatality"[Title/Abstract] OR "CFR Case Fatality Rate"[Title/Abstract] OR "Crude Death Rate"[Title/Abstract] OR "Crude Death Rates"[Title/Abstract] OR "Death Rate, Crude"[Title/Abstract] OR "Rate, Crude Death"[Title/Abstract] OR "Crude Mortality Rate"[Title/Abstract] OR "Crude Mortality Rates"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality Rate, Crude"[Title/Abstract] OR "Rate, Crude Mortality"[Title/Abstract] OR "Death Rate"[Title/Abstract] OR "Death Rates"[Title/Abstract] OR "Rate, Death"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality Rate"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality Rates"[Title/Abstract] OR "Rate, Mortality"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality, Excess"[Title/Abstract] OR "Excess Mortality"[Title/Abstract] OR "Excess Mortalities"[Title/Abstract] OR "Decline, Mortality"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality Declines"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality Decline"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality Determinants"[Title/Abstract] OR "Determinants, Mortality"[Title/Abstract] OR "Determinant, Mortality"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality Determinant"[Title/Abstract] OR "Mortality, Differential"[Title/Abstract] OR "Differential Mortality"[Title/Abstract] OR</p>	<p>450</p>
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	"Differential Mortalities"[Title/Abstract] OR "Age-Specific Death Rate"[Title/Abstract] OR "Age-Specific Death Rates"[Title/Abstract] OR "Death Rate, Age-Specific"[Title/Abstract] OR "Rate, Age-Specific Death"[Title/Abstract] OR "Age Specific Death Rate"[Title/Abstract] OR survival[Title/Abstract]))	
Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Dialyses, Renal" OR "Renal Dialyses" OR "Dialysis, Renal" OR hemodialysis OR hemodialyses OR "Dialysis, Extracorporeal" OR "Dialyses, Extracorporeal" OR "Extracorporeal Dialyses" OR "Extracorporeal Dialysis") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (erythropoietin OR "Epoetin Alfa" OR "Erythropoiesis stimulating agent" OR "Darbepoetin alfa" OR eprex) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (mortality OR mortalities OR "Case Fatality Rate" OR "Case Fatality Rates" OR "Rate, Case Fatality" OR "Rates, Case Fatality" OR "CFR Case Fatality Rate" OR "Crude Death Rate" OR "Crude Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Death" OR "Crude Mortality Rate" OR "Crude Mortality Rates" OR "Mortality Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Mortality" OR "Death Rate" OR "Death Rates" OR "Rate, Death" OR "Mortality Rate" OR "Mortality Rates" OR "Rate, Mortality" OR "Mortality, Excess" OR "Excess Mortality" OR "Excess Mortalities" OR "Decline, Mortality" OR "Mortality Declines" OR "Mortality Decline" OR "Mortality Determinants" OR "Determinants, Mortality" OR "Determinant, Mortality" OR "Mortality Determinant" OR "Mortality, Differential" OR "Differential Mortality" OR "Differential Mortalities" OR "Age-Specific Death Rate" OR "Age-Specific Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Age-Specific" OR survival))	1808
Science Direct	(("Renal Dialyses" OR Hemodialysis OR Hemodialyses) AND (erythropoietin OR "Epoetin Alfa" OR "Erythropoiesis stimulating agent") AND (mortality OR "Crude Death Rate" OR survival)	130
Cochrane Library	("Dialyses, Renal" OR "Renal Dialyses" OR "Dialysis, Renal" OR Hemodialysis OR Hemodialyses OR "Dialysis, Extracorporeal" OR "Dialyses, Extracorporeal" OR "Extracorporeal Dialyses" OR "Extracorporeal	165

	<p>Dialysis") in Title Abstract Keyword AND (erythropoietin OR "Epoetin Alfa" OR "Erythropoiesis stimulating agent" OR "Darbepoetin alfa" OR eprex) in Title Abstract Keyword AND (mortality OR Mortalities OR "Case Fatality Rate" OR "Case Fatality Rates" OR "Rate, Case Fatality" OR "Rates, Case Fatality" OR "CFR Case Fatality Rate" OR "Crude Death Rate" OR "Crude Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Death" OR "Crude Mortality Rate" OR "Crude Mortality Rates" OR "Mortality Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Mortality" OR "Death Rate" OR "Death Rates" OR "Rate, Death" OR "Mortality Rate" OR "Mortality Rates" OR "Rate, Mortality" OR "Mortality, Excess" OR "Excess Mortality" OR "Excess Mortalities" OR "Decline, Mortality" OR "Mortality Declines" OR "Mortality Decline" OR "Mortality Determinants" OR "Determinants, Mortality" OR "Determinant, Mortality" OR "Mortality Determinant" OR "Mortality, Differential" OR "Differential Mortality" OR "Differential Mortalities" OR "Age-Specific Death Rate" OR "Age-Specific Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Age-Specific" OR "Rate, Age-Specific Death" OR "Age Specific Death Rate" OR survival) in Title Abstract Keyword - (Word variations have been searched)</p>	
Google Scholar	<p>allintitle: ("Renal Dialyses" OR Hemodialysis OR Hemodialyses) AND (erythropoietin OR "Epoetin Alfa" OR "Erythropoiesis stimulating agent") AND (mortality OR "Crude Death Rate" OR survival)</p>	51
	<p>1: ((TS=("Dialyses, Renal" OR "Renal Dialyses" OR "Dialysis, Renal" OR Hemodialysis OR Hemodialyses OR "Dialysis, Extracorporeal" OR "Dialyses, Extracorporeal" OR "Extracorporeal Dialyses" OR "Extracorporeal Dialysis")) OR TI=("Dialyses, Renal" OR "Renal Dialyses" OR "Dialysis, Renal" OR Hemodialysis OR Hemodialyses OR "Dialysis, Extracorporeal" OR "Dialyses, Extracorporeal" OR "Extracorporeal Dialyses" OR "Extracorporeal Dialysis")) OR AB=("Dialyses, Renal" OR "Renal Dialyses" OR "Dialysis, Renal" OR Hemodialysis OR Hemodialyses OR "Dialysis, Extracorporeal" OR "Dialyses, Extracorporeal" OR "Extracorporeal Dialyses" OR "Extracorporeal Dialysis"))</p>	

Web Of Science	<p>2: ((TS= (erythropoietin OR "Epoetin Alfa" OR "Erythropoiesis stimulating agent" OR "Darbepoetin alfa" OR eplex)) OR TI= (erythropoietin OR "Epoetin Alfa" OR "Erythropoiesis stimulating agent" OR "Darbepoetin alfa" OR eplex)) OR AB= (erythropoietin OR "Epoetin Alfa" OR "Erythropoiesis stimulating agent" OR "Darbepoetin alfa" OR eprex))</p> <p>3: ((TS=(mortality OR Mortalities OR "Case Fatality Rate" OR "Case Fatality Rates" OR "Rate, Case Fatality" OR "Rates, Case Fatality" OR "CFR Case Fatality Rate" OR "Crude Death Rate" OR "Crude Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Death" OR "Crude Mortality Rate" OR "Crude Mortality Rates" OR "Mortality Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Mortality" OR "Death Rate" OR "Death Rates" OR "Rate, Death" OR "Mortality Rate" OR "Mortality Rates" OR "Rate, Mortality" OR "Mortality, Excess" OR "Excess Mortality" OR "Excess Mortalities" OR "Decline, Mortality" OR "Mortality Declines" OR "Mortality Decline" OR "Mortality Determinants" OR "Determinants, Mortality" OR "Determinant, Mortality" OR "Mortality Determinant" OR "Mortality, Differential" OR "Differential Mortality" OR "Differential Mortalities" OR "Age-Specific Death Rate" OR "Age-Specific Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Age-Specific" OR "Rate, Age-Specific Death" OR "Age Specific Death Rate" OR survival)) OR TI=(mortality OR Mortalities OR "Case Fatality Rate" OR "Case Fatality Rates" OR "Rate, Case Fatality" OR "Rates, Case Fatality" OR "CFR Case Fatality Rate" OR "Crude Death Rate" OR "Crude Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Death" OR "Crude Mortality Rate" OR "Crude Mortality Rates" OR "Mortality Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Mortality" OR "Death Rate" OR "Death Rates" OR "Rate, Death" OR "Mortality Rate" OR "Mortality Rates" OR "Rate, Mortality" OR "Mortality, Excess" OR "Excess Mortality" OR "Excess Mortalities" OR "Decline, Mortality" OR "Mortality Declines" OR "Mortality Decline" OR "Mortality Determinants" OR "Determinants, Mortality" OR "Determinant, Mortality" OR "Mortality Determinant" OR "Mortality, Differential" OR "Differential Mortality" OR "Differential</p>	1329
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	<p>Mortalities" OR "Age-Specific Death Rate" OR "Age-Specific Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Age-Specific" OR "Rate, Age-Specific Death" OR "Age Specific Death Rate" OR survival)) OR AB=(mortality OR Mortalities OR "Case Fatality Rate" OR "Case Fatality Rates" OR "Rate, Case Fatality" OR "Rates, Case Fatality" OR "CFR Case Fatality Rate" OR "Crude Death Rate" OR "Crude Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Death" OR "Crude Mortality Rate" OR "Crude Mortality Rates" OR "Mortality Rate, Crude" OR "Rate, Crude Mortality" OR "Death Rate" OR "Death Rates" OR "Rate, Death" OR "Mortality Rate" OR "Mortality Rates" OR "Rate, Mortality" OR "Mortality, Excess" OR "Excess Mortality" OR "Excess Mortalities" OR "Decline, Mortality" OR "Mortality Declines" OR "Mortality Decline" OR "Mortality Determinants" OR "Determinants, Mortality" OR "Determinant, Mortality" OR "Mortality Determinant" OR "Mortality, Differential" OR "Differential Mortality" OR "Differential Mortalities" OR "Age-Specific Death Rate" OR "Age-Specific Death Rates" OR "Death Rate, Age-Specific" OR "Rate, Age-Specific Death" OR "Age Specific Death Rate" OR survival)</p> <p>#1 AND #2 AND #3</p>	
Total		3933

Table 2: The results of the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS) for assessment of the quality of the observational studies (cohort, case-control, cross-sectional)

Number	Publication first author	Year	Components of the Newcastle Ottawa Scale (NOS) checklist			Total score
			Selection process	Comparability	Study design and results	
1	J. Möcks [19]	2000	3	2	3	8
2	Dennis J. Cotter [30]	2004	4	2	4	10
3	HAROLD I. FELDMAN [31]	2004	3	2	4	9
4	Deborah L. Regidor [11]	2006	3	1	3	7
5	Brian D. Bradbury [16]	2008	4	2	4	10
6	Elani Streja [32]	2008	3	2	4	9
7	Chang-Chyi Jenq [34]	2009	3	2	3	8
8	Yi Zhang [21]	2009	4	2	4	10
9	Huan-Cheng Chang [35]	2009	4	2	4	10
10	Brian D. Bradbury [20]	2009	4	2	3	9
11	Joseph M. Messana [36]	2009	4	2	2	8
12	Victor E Pollak [37]	2009	3	2	4	9
13	Ouhong Wang [38]	2010	4	2	4	10
14	Joan Fort [10]	2010	4	2	4	10
15	M. Alan Brookhart [17]	2010	4	2	3	9
16	Alexander Kainz [40]	2010	4	2	4	10
17	Paulo Roberto SANTOS [41]	2011	4	2	4	10
18	Yi Zhang [42]	2011	3	2	2	7
19	Eric D. Weinhandl [43]	2011	3	2	2	7
20	Vincenzo Panichi [44]	2011	4	2	3	9
21	Uyen Duong [45]	2012	4	1	4	9
22	Shingo Fukuma [46]	2012	4	2	4	10
23	Xavier Cuevas [47]	2012	4	2	4	10
24	Anuja Shah [48]	2012	4	2	3	9
25	Tetsuya Fujikawa [12]	2013	4	2	3	9

26	Junichi Ishigami [49]	2013	4	2	4	10
27	Angie Nishio [50]	2013	4	2	2	8
28	Wei Yang [22]	2013	4	2	2	8
29	Marit M Suttorp [51]	2013	4	2	4	10
30	Ben C. Wong [52]	2013	4	2	3	9
31	Nadiesda A. Costa [53]	2013	4	2	3	9
32	Tetsuya Ogawa [55]	2014	3	2	4	9
33	Andreas Schneider [56]	2014	4	2	3	9
34	Masayuki Okazaki [57]	2014	4	1	4	9
35	Takahiro Kuragano [58]	2014	3	1	3	7
36	Vincenzo Panichi[59]	2014	4	2	3	9
37	Owen Kwon [60]	2015	4	2	4	10
38	Rieko Eriguchi [61]	2015	3	1	4	8
39	Myoung Nam Bae [62]	2015	4	2	4	10
40	Masayuki Okazaki [63]	2015	4	2	4	10
41	Kunitoshi Iseki [64]	2015	3	2	3	8
42	Elani Streja [14]	2016	4	2	4	10
43	Jiacong Luo [65]	2016	3	2	4	9
44	Shunji Shiohira [66]	2016	3	2	4	9
45	Scott Sibbel [67]	2016	3	2	3	8
46	Zijin Chen [13]	2016	3	2	3	8
47	Rafael Perez-Garcia [18]	2017	4	1	3	8
48	Javier Varas [68]	2017	4	1	4	9
49	Nada Dimkovic [69]	2017	3	2	3	8
50	Ko-Lin Kuo [24]	2018	4	2	4	10
51	Toshihide Hayashi [70]	2019	3	2	4	9
52	Ling Sun [71]	2019	4	2	3	9
53	Angelo Karaboyas [72]	2019	4	2	4	10

54	Shu-Ching Yeh [73]	2019	4	2	4	10
55	Xiangxue Lu [74]	2020	4	2	4	10
56	Sai Pan [15]	2021	3	2	4	9
57	Kenichi Tanaka [75]	2021	4	2	4	10
58	Takahiro Yajima [76]	2021	4	2	4	10
59	Yukio Maruyama [77]	2021	4	2	4	10
60	Marisa Roldao [78]	2022	4	2	4	10
61	Hideki Fujii [79]	2022	4	2	4	10
62	Hyang Yun Lee [80]	2022	4	2	4	10
63	Shizuka Kobayashi [81]	2022	4	2	4	10

Table 3: The results of the Jadad scale for assessment of the quality of the randomized clinical trials (RCTs) studies

Number	Publication first author	Year	Components of the Jadad checklist								Total score
			Mention of randomization	Correct explanation of the randomization method	Mention of blinding	Correct explanation of the blinding method	The number and reason for loss to follow-up	Mention of the inclusion and exclusion criteria	Evaluate and mention side effects caused by therapeutic intervention	Examines the description of the statistical methods	
1	J. Bahlmann [39]	1991	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
2	Ryan D. Kilpatrick [33]	2008	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
3	Joanne H. Lau [49]	2010	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	7
4	Andreas Schneider [64]	2013	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	8
5	Valeria Saglimbene [33]	2017	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	7

Table 4: Prevalence of underlying diseases in the study population in each of the studies included in the meta-analysis

Number	First author	Underlying disease	Percent (%)
1	Owen Kwon [60]	History of diabetes	52.4
		Coronary artery disease	12.3
		Congestive heart failure	11.3
		Arrhythmia	1.87
		Cerebrovascular disease	2.3
		Peripheral vascular disease	6.2
2	M. Alan Brookhart [17]	History of ischemic heart disease	24.4
		History of stroke	9.5
		History of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	7.8
		History of congestive heart failure	33.4
		History of peripheral vascular disease	14.5
3	Angie Nishio [50]	Diabetes mellitus	56.3
		Hypertension	73.1
		Cardiovascular disease	31
		Peripheral arterial disease	17.3
		Heart failure	16.7
		Dyslipidemia	35.8
4	Andreas Schneider [54]	coronary artery disease	28.5
		Congestive heart failure	35.4
		Peripheral vascular disease	44.6
5	Xiangxue Lu [74]	Diabetic nephropathy	18.8
		Hypertensive nephrosclerosis	13.4
		Chronic interstitial nephritis	7.6
6		Coronary artery disease	22.4

	Kunitoshi Iseki [64]	Cancer (other than skin)	7.8
		Other CVD	23.1
		Cerebrovascular disease	8.9
		Congestive heart failure	15.8
		Diabetes mellitus	29.5
		Gastrointestinal bleeding	2.4
		HIV	0.5
		Hypertension	69.7
		Lung disease	2
		Neurologic disorder	8.9
		Psychological disorder	2.6
		Peripheral vascular disease	9.6
		Recurrent cellulitis	2
7	Toshihide Hayashi [70]	Diabetes	60
		Malignancy	17
8	Joseph M. Messana [36]	Diabetes mellitus	61.4
		Ischemic heart disease	56.5
		Congestive heart failure	61.7
		Pericarditis	2.3
		Cardiac arrhythmia	41.7
		Cardiac arrest	2
		Cerebrovascular disease	33.3
		Peripheral vascular disease	49.3
		Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	36
		Malignant neoplasm	21.5
		Septicemia/septic shock	18.5
		Pneumonia	4
		Gastrointestinal bleed within 3 mo	2.4
Gastrointestinal/no hemorrhage within 6 mo	1.1		
Sickle cell anemia	3		

9	Kenichi Tanaka [75]	History of cardiovascular disease	19.7
		Diabetes	44.9
10	Victor E Pollak [37]	Arteriosclerotic heart disease	23.1
		Cerebral vascular disease	8.3
		Peripheral vascular	12.1
		Malignant disease	9.1
		AIDS	4.2
		Diabetes mellitus Type I	4.62
		Diabetes mellitus Type II	37.8
		Peptic ulcer disease	2.1
		Previous kidney transplant	4.2
11	Yukio Maruyama [77]	Acute myocardial infarction	9.2
		Cerebral hemorrhage	5.9
		Cerebral infarction	18.4
		Quadruple amputation	3.4
12	Shingo Fukuma [46]	Diabetes	32.5
		History of CVD	19.5
13	Brian D. Bradbury [20]	Diabetes as primary cause of ESRD	35.2
14	Andreas Schneider [56]	Coronary artery disease	25.5
		Congestive heart failure	47.9
		Peripheral vascular disease	44.7
15	Eric D. Weinhandl [43]	Diabetes	41.7
		Hypertension	30.6
16	Marit M Suttorp [51]	Diabetes mellitus	17.1
		Malignancy	7.4
		Cardiovascular disease	39.2
17	Ko-Lin Kuo [24]	Diabetes mellitus	45.4
		Hypertension	44.8
18	Vincenzo Panichi [44]	CVD	26
		Diabetes	18.8

		Hypertension	35
		Malignancy	13.9
19	Jiacong Luo [65]	Cancer	3.1
		Cerebrovascular disease	0.8
		COPD	5
		Congestive heart failure	14.5
		Coronary artery disease	7.6
		Diabetes	68.6
		Gastrointestinal bleeding	1.5
		HIV/AIDS	0.9
		Hypertension	35.2
		Non-kidney disease-related anemia	2.1
		Peripheral vascular disease	2.9
20	Zijin Chen [13]	-	-
21	Ryan D. Kilpatrick [33]	Diabetes mellitus	54
		Current hypertension	70
		Peripheral vascular disease	40
		Cardiac-related hospitalizations	73
22	Paulo Roberto SANTOS [41]	Glomerulonephritis	43.6
		Hypertension	23.7
		Diabetes	9
		Polycystic kidney	7.1
		Obstructive uropathy	4.5
		Lupus	2.6
		Chronic pyelonephritis	2.6
Undetermined	7.1		
23	Angelo Karaboyas [72]	Diabetes	62
		Hypertension	87
		Congestive heart failure	27
		Peripheral vascular disease	16

		Cancer (non-skin)	11
24	HAROLD I. FELDMAN [31]	Diabetes	44.7
25	Elani Streja [14]	Diabetes mellitus	57
		Hypertension	79
		Ischemic heart disease	21
		Congestive heart failure	28
		Peripheral vascular disease	11
		Cerebrovascular accident	7
		Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	6
26	Elani Streja [32]	Malignancy	5
		Heart failure	53
		Peripheral vascular disease	23
		Ischemic heart disease	35
27	Masayuki Okazaki [57]	Myocardial infarct	12
		Diabetes	48.8
		Hypertension	73.32
		Dyslipidemia	28.51
28	Valeria Saglimbene [23]	Diabetes	24.39
		Chronic lung disease	13.11
		Ischemic heart disease	21.34
		Transient ischemic attack	4.24
		Heart failure	7.93
		Cardiac arrhythmia	13.11
		Seizures	1.07
		Thromboembolic event	5.03
		Wait-listing for kidney	10.52
		Previous kidney transplantation	10.82
		29	Anuja Shah [48]
Cancer	12.9		
Atherosclerotic heart disease	47.7		

		Heart failure	37.7
		COPD	13.7
		Cerebrovascular disease	19.9
		History of hypertension	78.2
		No ambulatory	3.4
		Other heart diseases	19.4
		Peripheral vascular disease	15.5
30	Junichi Ishigami [49]	Diabetes	37.54
31	Myoung Nam Bae [62]	Previous cardiovascular diseases history	17.9
		Diabetes mellitus	48.5
32	J. Möcks [19]	Hypertension	45.7
		Heart disease	33.2
		Endocrine/nutritional/metabolic/immune disease	23.1
		Digestive system disease	22.7
		Nervous system disease	12.9
		Diabetes	11.5
		Infection	9.9
33	Huan-Cheng Chang [35]	Hypertension or type 2 diabetes mellitus	27.98
34	Shu-Ching Yeh [73]	Diabetes	12
		Hypertension	41
		Congestive heart failure	9
		Left ventricular hypertrophy	12
		Cerebral vascular accident	7
		Coronary artery disease	11
		Myocardial infarction	3
35	Shunji Shiohira [66]	History of CVD	11.2
36	Hideki Fujii [79]	Hypertension	80.2
		Diabetes mellitus	41.5
		Cardiovascular disease	52.1

		Renin-angiotensin-aldosterone inhibitor	51.8
37	Uyen Duong [45]	-	-
38	Joan Fort [10]	-	-
39	Marisa Roldao [78]	Diabetes mellitus	39
		Congestive heart failure	61
		Hypertension	71.2
40	Chang-Chyi Jenq [34]	Previous cardiovascular disease	11.8
		Hypertension	33.2
41	Takahiro Yajima [76]	Hypertension	95.6
		Diabetes	46.7
		History of cardiovascular disease	67.8
42	Joanne H. Lau [39]	Coronary artery disease	39.6
		Diabetes mellitus	34.4
43	Ouhong Wang [38]	Diabetes	50.9
		Hypertension	15.4
44	Nada Dimkovic [69]	-	-
45	Sai Pan [15]	-	-
46	Ben C. Wong [52]	Ischemic heart disease	29
		Congestive heart failure	21
		Atrial fibrillation/flutter	11
		Stroke/TIA	2
		Peripheral vascular disease	7
		Diabetes	56
		Hypertension	95
		Malignancy	6
47	Yi Zhang [42]	Cardiovascular comorbidities	41.95
48	Hyang Yun Lee [80]	Diabetes	59.3
49	Masayuki Okazaki [63]	Diabetes	48.3
		Cardiovascular disease	26.2
50	Ling Sun [71]	Hypertension	88.68

		Diabetes mellites	20.75
		Chronic heart failure	29.56
		Strokea	18.24
		Arrhythmia	3.14
		Gastrointestinal bleeding	11.32
51	Alexander Kainz [40]	Diabetes	26.18
		COPD	9.34
		Heart disease	38.2
		Hypertension	78.43
		Liver disease	7.08
		Neoplasia	9.66
		Vascular disease	30.47
52	Takahiro Kuragano [58]	-	-
53	Deborah L. Regidor [11]	Diabetes	42.5
54		Diabetes	69.11
		Congestive heart failure	12.55
55	Scott Sibbel [67]	Coronary artery disease	7.90
		Cerebrovascular disease	0.77
		Cancer	2.04
		Infection	0.7
		Peripheral vascular disease	2.63
56	Vincenzo Panichi[59]	CVD	26
		Diabetes	18.8
		Hypertension	35
		Malignancy	13.9
57	J. Bahlmann [29]	Hypertension	46
		Coronary heart disease	22
		Coronary insufficiency	13
		Arrhythmias	11
		Valvular heart disease	2

		Diabetes mellitus	27
58	Javier Varas [68]	-	-
59	Shizuka Kobayashi [81]	Cerebrovascular disease	19.43
		Diabetes	50.29
60	Brian D. Bradbury [16]	-	-
61	Yi Zhang [21]	Cardiovascular comorbidities	63.1
62	Wei Yang [22]	Atherosclerotic heart disease	51
		Congestive heart failure	53
		Cardiovascular accident/transient ischemic attack	27.1
		Peripheral vascular disease	47.8
		Other cardiac	51.2
		Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	26.9
		Gastrointestinal bleed	18
		Liver disease	15.3
		Dysrhythmia	38.3
		Cancer	13.4
		Diabetes	63.1
63	Rafael Perez-Garcia [18]	-	-
64	Tetsuya Ogawa [55]	Diabetes	34
65	Rieko Eriguchi [61]	Diabetes	30.03
		History of cardiovascular disease	32.27
66	Dennis J. Cotter [30]	Atherosclerotic heart disease	41.7
		Cardiovascular accident–transient ischemic attack	16.6
		Congestive heart failure	47
		Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease	13.5
		Cancer	12.9
		Gastrointestinal diseases with bleeding	7.6
		Other cardiac diseases	27
67	Tetsuya Fujikawa [12]	Coronary artery disease	40.4

		Cancer, other than skin	9.6
		Other CVD	31.7
		Cerebrovascular disease	13.9
		Congestive heart failure	25
		Diabetes mellitus	34.4
		Gastrointestinal bleeding	4.5
		HIV	0.5
		Hypertension	73
		Lung disease	2.5
		Neurologic disorder	9.8
		Psychological disorder	3.4
		Peripheral vascular disease Recurrent cellulitis	17.6
		Recurrent cellulitis	3.6
68	Nadiesda A. Costa [53]	Diabetic	42
69	Xavier Cuevas [47]	-	-

Table 5. Characteristics of the studies included in the meta-analysis to investigate the relationship between receiving ESAs and mortality in hemodialysis patients.

Number	Authors	Year	Study design	Study setting	Sample size	RR	95 % CI	mean follow-up (Months)	Quality score
1	J. Bahlmann [29]	1991	RCTs	German	129	1.05	0.74-14.89	6	8*
2	J. Möcks [19]	2000	Cohort	German	3111	0.81	0.51-1.37	12	8
3	Dennis J. Cotter [30]	2004	Cohort	US	31301	1.67	1.35-2.06	12	10
4	HAROLD I. FELDMAN [31]	2004	Cohort	US	27280	1.02	0.86-1.22	6	9
5	Deborah L. Regidor [11]	2006	Cohort	US	58058	1.23	1.14-1.33	24	7
6	Brian D. Bradbury [16]	2008	Cohort	US	22955	0.93	0.92-0.95	12	10
7	Elani Streja [32]	2008	Cohort	US	32418	1.59	1.54-1.65	3	9
8	Ryan D. Kilpatrick [33]	2008	RCTs	US	321	0.69	0.47-1.01	12	8*
9	Chang-Chyi Jenq [34]	2009	Cohort	Taiwan	187	1.014	1.002-1.026	12	8
10	Yi Zhang [21]	2009	Cohort	US	18454	1.01	0.87-1.17	9	10
11	Huan-Cheng Chang [35]	2009	Cohort	Taiwan	702	2.07	1.58-2.63	46.08	10
12	Brian D. Bradbury [20]	2009	Cohort	US	6133	0.9	0.79-1.02	6	9
13	Joseph M. Messana [36]	2009	Cross-sectional	US	393967	1.43	1.25-1.63	-	8
14	Victor E Pollak [37]	2009	Cohort	US	1774	1.41	1.19-1.66	6	9
15	Ouhong Wang [38]	2010	Cohort	US	27791	1.18	1.02-1.36	12	10
16	Joan Fort [10]	2010	Cohort	Spanish	2310	0.76	0.64-0.9	24	10

17	Joanne H. Lau [39]	2010	RCTs	Canada	154	1.12	1.01-1.24	72	7*
18	M. Alan Brookhart [17]	2010	Cohort	US	269717	0.96	0.95-0.98	12	9
19	Alexander Kainz [40]	2010	Cohort	Austrian	932	2	1.47-2.72	48	10
20	Paulo Roberto SANTOS [41]	2011	Cohort	Brazil	156	5.172	1.663-16.081	12	10
21	Yi Zhang [42]	2011	Cohort	US	35593	1.17	1.05-1.3	9	7
22	Eric D. Weinhandl [43]	2011	Cohort	US	137918	1.07	0.96-1.18	36	7
23	Vincenzo Panichi [44]	2011	Cohort	Italy	753	1.62	1.18-2.23	36	9
24	Uyen Duong [45]	2012	Cohort	US	139103	1.56	1.09-2.22	22.83	9
25	Shingo Fukuma [46]	2012	Cohort	Japan	95460	1.56	1.22-1.99	12	10
26	Xavier Cuevas [47]	2012	Cohort	Spanish	2310	1.15	0.98-1.36	24	10
27	Anuja Shah [48]	2012	Cohort	US	2402	0.74	0.59-0.91	26.26	9
28	Tetsuya Fujikawa [12]	2013	Cohort	Japan	2104	2.33	1.33-4.07	27.45	9
29	Junichi Ishigami [49]	2013	Cohort	Japan	349	2.73	1.2-6.24	24	10
30	Angie Nishio [50]	2013	Cohort	US	606	1.85	1.44-2.4	30	8
31	Wei Yang [22]	2013	Cohort	US	409 364	0.98	0.89-1.08	22.7	8
32	Marit M Suttorp [51]	2013	Cohort	Netherland	1013	1.27	1.08-1.49	60	10
33	Ben C. Wong [52]	2013	Cohort	Canada	484	1.6	0.76-3.61	3	9
34	Nadiesda A. Costa [53]	2013	Cohort	US	36450	1.89	1.67-2.15	6	9
35	Andreas Schneider [54]	2013	RCTs	German	1015	1.77	1.23-2.54	48	8*
36	Tetsuya Ogawa [55]	2014	Cohort	Japan	320	1.86	1.25-2.57	70.4	9

37	Andreas Schneider [56]	2014	Cohort	German	1255	1.25	1.18-1.32	48	9
38	Masayuki Okazaki [57]	2014	Cohort	Japan	248	4.204	1.173-15.065	24	9
39	Takahiro Kuragano [58]	2014	Cohort	Japan	1095	1.71	0.48-6.07	24	7
40	Vincenzo Panichi[59]	2014	Cohort	Italy	753	1.01	1.006-1.025	84	9
41	Owen Kwon [60]	2015	Cohort	Korea	1276	1.81	1.1-2.98	19.4	10
42	Rieko Eriguchi [61]	2015	Cohort	Japan	2905	1.41	1.18-1.69	48	8
43	Myoung Nam Bae [62]	2015	Cohort	Korea	1594	1.72	1.1-2.68	40	10
44	Masayuki Okazaki [63]	2015	Cohort	Japan	298	1.9	0.92-3.93	34.6	10
45	Kunitoshi Iseki [64]	2015	Cohort	Japan	1525	0.899	0.49-1.648	36	8
46	Elani Streja [14]	2016	Cohort	US	128598	1.2	1.05-1.37	60	10
47	Jiacong Luo [65]	2016	Cohort	US	98972	1.64	1.39-1.94	21	9
48	Shunji Shiohira [66]	2016	Cohort	Japan	375	3.64	2.03-6.28	36	9
49	Scott Sibbel [67]	2016	Cohort	US	99294	0.94	0.76-1.18	12	8
50	Zijin Chen [13]	2016	Cohort	China	250	2.22	1.18-4.17	36	8
51	Rafael Perez-Garcia [18]	2017	Cohort	Spanish	1679	1.47	1.11-1.94	27.7	8
52	Valeria Saglimbene [23]	2017	RCTs	Italy	656	0.98	0.64-1.52	12	7*
53	Javier Varas [68]	2017	Cohort	Spanish	1679	1.97	0.75-5.14	17.79	9
54	Nada Dimkovic [69]	2017	Cohort	US	603	1.225	0.704-2.129	12	8
55	Ko-Lin Kuo [24]	2018	Cohort	Taiwan	42 230	0.99	0.94-1.05	41	10
56	Toshihide Hayashi [70]	2019	Cohort	Japan	108	2.25	1.25-4.06	37.2	9
57	Ling Sun [71]	2019	Cohort	China	159	1.112	1.029-1.202	24	9

58	Angelo Karaboyas [72]	2019	Cohort	US	4604	1.06	0.88-1.29	8	10
59	Shu-Ching Yeh [73]	2019	Cohort	Taiwan	1346	0.76	0.35-1.65	37	10
60	Xiangxue Lu [74]	2020	Cohort	China	276	1.781	1.091-2.91	55	10
61	Sai Pan [15]	2021	Cohort	China	824	1.62	1.26-2.08	12	9
62	Kenichi Tanaka [75]	2021	Cohort	Japan	127	2.57	1.05-6.27	55.2	10
63	Takahiro Yajima [76]	2021	Cohort	Japan	180	1.06	1.03-1.08	55.2	10
64	Yukio Maruyama [77]	2021	Cohort	Japan	149308	1.025	1.021-1.029	12	10
65	Marisa Roldao [78]	2022	Cohort	Portugal	59	5.4	1.31-22.32	3	10
66	Hideki Fujii [79]	2022	Cohort	Japan	3312	1.42	1.1-1.84	24	10
67	Hyang Yun Lee [80]	2022	Cohort	Korea	123	4.4	1.2-16.1	24	10
68	Shizuka Kobayashi [81]	2022	Cohort	Japan	175	5.51	1.71-17.78	24	10

*Jadad scale

Table 6. Adjusted variables to investigate the relationship between receiving ESAs and the mortality of hemodialysis patients in the articles included in the study

Number	Publication first author	Year	Adjusted variables
1	J. Bahlmann [29]	1991	-
2	J. Möcks [19]	2000	-
3	Dennis J. Cotter [30]	2004	Age, sex, race, primary diagnosis, and comorbidities.
4	HAROLD I. FELDMAN [31]	2004	Iron, gender, race, age, Duration of ESRD, diabetic status, hospitalizations, IV antibiotic doses administered, URR, Albumin, AST/SGOT, Bicarbonate, Ferritin, Hemoglobin and Phosphate.
5	Deborah L. Regidor [11]	2006	-
6	Brian D. Bradbury [16]	2008	Age, sex, race, body mass index, region, diabetes status, dialysis vintage, urea reduction ratio, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, albumin level, calcium level, ferritin level, Hb level, phosphorus level, parathyroid hormone level, transferrin saturation, number of hospitalizations, number of hospitalization days, number of unexcused missed dialysis visits, number of EPO dose changes, and percentage of time with Hb level less than 11 g/dL (\downarrow 110 g/L).
7	Elani Streja [32]	2008	-
8	Ryan D. Kilpatrick [33]	2008	Age, gender, race, diabetes mellitus, and dialysis vintage
9	Chang-Chyi Jenq [34]	2009	-
10	Yi Zhang [21]	2009	Age, race, gender, underlying cause of ESRD, geographic region, Charlson index score, cardiovascular and non-cardiovascular comorbidities, baseline hematocrit, average intravenous iron administered inpatient stays in the baseline, and average epoetin dosage and number of administrations at baseline
11	Huan-Cheng Chang [35]	2009	Age, chronic glomerulonephritis and etiology, and Fe or vitamin D3

12	Brian D. Bradbury [20]	2009	Age, race, gender, body mass index, diabetes, vascular access type, albumin, ferritin, Mean hemoglobin, transferrin saturation, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, missed EPO administrations, iron dose, and hospitalizations
13	Joseph M. Messana [36]	2009	Demographic, anthropometric, and Medicare claims data, EPO, iron, and vitamin D analogues
14	Victor E Pollak [37]	2009	Age, major co-morbid conditions, IV iron, Hb, TSAT, Serum ferritin, Serum albumin, Kt/V
15	Ouhong Wang [38]	2010	Hemoglobin level and epoetin alfa dose 2, 4, 6, and 8 wk before exposure, days in the hospital, number of epoetin alfa doses administered outside the hospital, albumin, ferritin, TSAT, vascular access type, hypertension, and dialysis adequacy 2 wk before exposure.
16	Joan Fort [10]	2010	Age, functional status, body mass index, albumin levels, catheter as vascular access, and previous history of cardiovascular disease
17	Joanne H. Lau [39]	2010	Age, DM, CAD, pulse pressure, gender, average Hgb, and serum albumin
18	M. Alan Brookhart [17]	2010	Race, age, sex, geographic region indicator variables, body mass index, serum albumin, calendar year, cause of end-stage renal disease, history of ischemic heart disease, and history of stroke
19	Alexander Kainz [40]	2010	-
20	Paulo Roberto SANTOS [41]	2011	Age, high-grade comorbidity, and mean hemoglobin
21	Yi Zhang [42]	2011	-
22	Eric D. Weinhandl [43]	2011	-
23	Vincenzo Panichi [44]	2011	Age, albumin, CVD, and CRP
24	Uyen Duong [45]	2012	Age, gender, race/ethnicity, ten pre-existing comorbid conditions, history of tobacco smoking, categories of dialysis vintage, primary insurance, marital status, presence of diabetes, serum ferritin and iron saturation, body mass index, serum levels of albumin, total iron-binding capacity, creatinine, phosphorus, calcium, bicarbonate, blood white blood cell count and lymphocyte percentage.
25	Shingo Fukuma [46]	2012	Age, sex, time on dialysis therapy, post-dialysis body weight, diabetes, history of cardiovascular disease, serum albumin level, and transferrin saturation.
26	Xavier Cuevas [47]	2012	Gender, alcohol consumption, nephrologist follow-up time, CKD etiology, previous cardiac arrhythmia, SBP before HD session, hemodialysis technique, HD intolerance, glucose,

			phosphorus, hemoglobin, potassium, AST, phosphorus binder drugs, cardiovascular drugs, and vitamin D analogs/metabolites.
27	Anuja Shah [48]	2012	Hemoglobin categories and change of hemoglobin categories and entry calendar quarter plus age, gender, presence of diabetes, race/ethnicity (African Americans and other self-categorized Blacks, Non-Hispanic Caucasians, Asians, Hispanics, and others), categories of dialysis vintage (<6 months, 6–12 months, 12–24 months, and ≥2 years), primary insurance (Medicare, Medicaid, and others), and marital status (married, single, divorced, and widowed), type of vascular access (catheter, AVF, and graft), dialysis dose as indicated by Kt/V (single pool), 10 preexisting comorbid conditions, history of tobacco smoking.
28	Tetsuya Fujikawa [12]	2013	Age, PCR, albumin, CRP, and phosphorus. Sex, ferritin, and comorbidities
29	Junichi Ishigami [49]	2013	Dialysis period, age, sex, Diabetes mellitus, serum albumin, serum CRP and serum ferritin
30	Angie Nishio [50]	2013	Age, sex, race, comorbidities, dialysis vintage (years on dialysis), type of vascular access, use of renin angiotensin blockers, serum albumin and Kt/V
31	Wei Yang [22]	2013	-
32	Marit M Suttorp [51]	2013	Age, sex, weight, primary kidney disease, diabetes mellitus, malignancy, cardiovascular disease. 2 Additional adjusted for weekly Kt/V urea, GFR, nutritional status, albumin, ferritin, PTH, and CRP.
33	Ben C. Wong [52]	2013	-
34	Nadiesda A. Costa [53]	2013	Age, gender, weight, race/ethnicity, hemodialysis vintage, hemodialysis catheter, diabetes status, and donor type.
35	Andreas Schneider [54]	2013	-
36	Tetsuya Ogawa [55]	2014	Age, sex, dialysis vintage, body mass index, and serum albumin
37	Andreas Schneider [56]	2014	Age, sex, Atorvastatin, and 25 (OH) D.
38	Masayuki Okazaki [57]	2014	Age and serum levels of albumin and CRP
39	Takahiro Kuragano [58]	2014	-
40	Vincenzo Panichi [59]	2014	Age, dialysis vintage, Charlson index, GNRI quartiles, nPCR, and CRP

41	Owen Kwon [60]	2015	Age, sex, dialysis vintage, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, albumin, high-sensitivity C-reactive protein and ferritin and adjusted transferrin saturation (TSAT)
42	Rieko Eriguchi [61]	2015	Age, sex, dialysis duration, pre-dialysis systolic blood pressure, antihypertensive agent use, diabetes, history of cardiovascular disease, serum albumin, serum calcium, serum phosphorus, serum total cholesterol, log-transformed serum C-reactive protein, log-transformed serum ferritin, body mass index, and Kt/V
43	Myoung Nam Bae [62]	2015	Age, gender, diabetes mellitus, previous cardiovascular disease history, duration of dialysis, serum level of iron, ferritin, albumin, intact PTH, hs-CRP, total cholesterol, and Kt/V.
44	Masayuki Okazaki [63]	2015	Age, gender, geriatric nutritional index, diabetes, diastolic BP, protein catabolic rate, and Ferritin
45	Kunitoshi Iseki [64]	2015	JESS, Elderly group, Vintage, male gender, primary disease, comorbidities, congestive heart failure cancer, hypertension, neurologic disorder, CVD, BMI, Albumin, Dialysis time, Dialysis frequency, Single pool Kt/V, and Hypnotic agent
46	Elani Streja [14]	2016	Age, sex, race/ethnicity (Caucasian, African American, Hispanic, Asian, and others), marital status (married, divorced, single, and widowed), primary insurance (Medicare, Medicaid, private insurance, and others), comorbid conditions, calendar quarter of cohort entry, and dialysis vintage (<6months, 6monthsto <24 months, 2to <5years, and ≥ 5 years), diabetes mellitus, hypertension, ischemic heart disease, congestive heart failure, cerebrovascular disease, peripheral vascular disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, malignancy, non-ambulatory state, and current smoking status, Hb level, serum albumin, creatinine, calcium, phosphorus, bicarbonate, total iron binding capacity, ferritin, white blood cell count, lymphocyte percentage, normalized protein nitrogen appearance (a metric of dietary protein intake), dialysis adequacy (single-pool <i>Kt/V</i>), and body mass index
47	Jiacong Luo [65]	2016	Age, sex, cause of end-stage renal disease, dialysis vintage, vascular access, cancer, cerebrovascular disease, heart failure, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, coronary artery disease, gastrointestinal bleeding, human immunodeficiency virus/AIDS, peripheral vascular disease, intravenous (IV) antibiotic use, dry weight, serum ferritin level, saturated transferrin, parathyroid hormone level, albumin level, IV vitamin D use, and Comorbidity Index score.
48	Shunji Shiohira [66]	2016	Age, serum albumin and C-reactive protein levels, and history of CVD
49	Scott Sibbel [67]	2016	Age, race, etiology, weight, vintage, access, diabetes, congestive heart failure, cerebrovascular disease, alcohol abuse, peripheral vascular disease, and Charlson comorbidity index
50	Zijin Chen [13]	2016	Age and gender
51	Rafael Perez-Garcia [18]	2017	Age (years), CCI, VA, gender, and BMI (kg/m ²). ‘C-M’ denotes case-mix adjusted. This model incorporates the demographics-adjusted model and data for CRP (mg/L), hemoglobin (g/dL), Kt (L), and iron dose (mg/month)

52	Valeria Saglimbene [23]	2017	-
53	Javier Varas [68]	2017	-
54	Nada Dimkovic [69]	2017	Demographic factors, comorbidities, dialysis adequacy, and biochemical data.
55	Ko-Lin Kuo [24]	2018	Age, sex, diabetes, hypertension, dialysis adequacy (Kt/V), eGFR at the start of dialysis (MDRD), white blood cell counts, the normalized protein catabolic rate (nPCR), serum albumin, cholesterol, triglyceride, hemoglobin, ferritin, transferrin saturation, calcium, phosphate, alkaline phosphatase, intact-PTH, uric acid, and intravenous iron use
56	Toshihide Hayashi [70]	2019	Age, sex, diabetes, malignancy, eGFR, Hb, TSAT, ferritin, CRP, and intact PTH
57	Ling Sun [71]	2019	Age, hemoglobin, ferritin, TSAT, ERI, hs-CRP, pre-dialysis creatinine, albumin, and intact PTH
58	Angelo Karaboyas [72]	2019	IV iron dose
59	Shu-Ching Yeh [73]	2019	Age and sex, comorbidities such as type 2 diabetes, hypertension, congestive heart failure, left ventricular hypertrophy, cerebrovascular accident, coronary artery disease, myocardial infarction, hepatitis B, hepatitis C, and antihypertensive agents, laboratory parameters including the values of aspartate transaminase, alanine transaminase, uric acid, albumin, hematocrit, calcium, phosphorus, intact parathyroid hormone, alkaline phosphatase, and kt/V.
60	Xiangxue Lu [74]	2020	Pre-dialysis serum albumin, high-sensitivity C-reaction protein, magnesium, pre-dialysis serum ferritin, serum transferrin saturation, pre-dialysis corrected calcium, phosphorus, high-density lipoprotein, low-density lipoprotein, total cholesterol, and triglyceride
61	Sai Pan [15]	2021	Age, gender, BMI, the primary cause of ESRD, and comorbid CCVDs; type of VA, Kt/v; (iv) f hemoglobin level and iron dosage; and levels of serum albumin, serum phosphate, and serum calcium
62	Kenichi Tanaka [75]	2021	Age, sex, dialysis facility, diabetes, history of cardiovascular disease, dialysis duration, calcium, phosphorus, albumin, hemoglobin, C-reactive protein, intact parathyroid hormone, transferrin saturation, ferritin, use of angiotensin receptor blocker or angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitor, and Kt/V
63	Takahiro Yajima [76]	2021	Age, history of cardiovascular disease, creatinine, and C-reactive protein

64	Yukio Maruyama [77]	2021	Age, sex, dialysis duration, body weight, underlying disease, and comorbid disease,
65	Marisa Roldao [78]	2022	Charlson Comorbidity Index, central venous catheter
66	Hideki Fujii [79]	2022	Major adverse cardiovascular events, Cardiac events, Heart failure
67	Hyang Yun Lee [80]	2022	Age, sex, and modified Charlson comorbidity index
68	Shizuka Kobayashi [81]	2022	Age, dialysis history, body mass index (BMI) (median), sex, and diabetes mellitus (DM)

Table 7. Sample size, number of patients, gender ratio, number of men and women in each of the studies included in the analysis

Number	First authors	Study type	Sample size	Total hemodialysis	Male	Female	Gender ratio
1	Tetsuya Fujikawa	Cohort	2104	2104	1296	808	1.60396
2	Jiacong Luo	Cohort	98972	98972	53939	45033	1.197766
3	Chang-Chyi Jenq	Cohort	187	187	77	110	0.7
4	Toshihide Hayashi	Cohort	108	108	61	47	1.297872
5	Sai Pan	Cohort	824	824	432	392	1.102041
6	Shunji Shiohira	Cohort	375	375	242	133	1.819549
7	Tetsuya Ogawa	Cohort	320	320	210	110	1.909091
8	Ouhong Wang	Cohort	27791	27791	14516	13275	1.093484
9	Paulo Roberto SANTOS	Cohort	156	156	95	61	1.557377
10	Joan Fort	Cohort	2310	2310			
11	Uyen Duong	Cohort	139103	139103	76507	62596	1.222235
12	Valeria Saglimbene	RCTs	656	656	404	252	1.603175
13	Andreas Schneider	Cohort	1255	1255	680	575	1.182609
14	Owen Kwon	Cohort	1276	1276	745	531	1.403013
15	Rafael Perez-Garcia	Cohort	1679	1679	1092	587	1.860307
16	Junichi Ishigami	Cohort	349	349	216	133	1.62406
17	Joanne H. Lau	RCTs	154	154	91	63	1.444444
18	Kenichi Tanaka	Cohort	127	127	70	57	1.22807
19	Rieko Eriguchi	Cohort	2905	2905	1651	1254	1.316587
20	Angie Nishio	Cohort	606	606	339	267	1.269663
21	Xiangxue Lu	Cohort	276	276	150	126	1.190476
22	Yi Zhang	Cohort	35593	35593	17873	17720	1.008634
23	Dennis J. Cotter	Cohort	31301	31301	15764	15537	1.01461
24	Wei Yang	Cohort		409 364	215146	194218	1.107755
25	Brian D. Bradbury	Cohort	22955	22955	11705	11250	1.040444
26	Yi Zhang	Cohort	18454	18454	9448	9006	1.049078
27	Elani Streja	Cohort	32418	32418			
28	Masayuki Okazaki	Cohort	248	248	160	88	1.818182
29	Elani Streja	Cohort	128598	128598	58289	70309	0.8290404
30	Shingo Fukuma	Cohort	95460	95460	56321	39139	1.438999

31	Marit M Suttorp	Cohort	1013	1013	600	413	1.452785
32	Huan-Cheng Chang	Cohort	702	702	335	367	0.9128065
33	Brian D. Bradbury	Cohort	6133	6133	2944	3189	0.9231734
34	M. Alan Brookhart	Cohort	269717	269717	144272	125445	1.150082
35	J. Möcks	Cohort	3111	3111	1378	1733	0.7951529
36	Deborah L. Regidor	Cohort	58058	58058	31057	27001	1.150217
37	Takahiro Yajima	Cohort	180	180	123	57	2.157895
38	Joseph M. Messina	Cross-sectional	393967	393967	209985	183982	1.141335
39	Eric D. Weinhandl	Cohort	137918	137918	71717	66201	1.083322
40	Alexander Kainz	Cohort	932	932	512	420	1.219048
41	Myoung Nam Bae	Cohort	1594	1594	904	690	1.310145
42	Vincenzo Panichi	Cohort	753	753	457	296	1.543919
43	HAROLD I. FELDMAN	Cohort	27280	27280	13744	13536	1.015366
44	Scott Sibbel	Cohort	99294	99294	54115	45179	1.197791
45	Ryan D. Kilpatrick	RCTs	321	321	167	154	1.084416
46	Masayuki Okazaki	Cohort	298	298	187	111	1.684685
47	Ben C. Wong	Cohort	484	484	273	211	1.293839
48	Javier Varas	Cohort	1679	1679	1087	592	1.836149
49	Takahiro Kuragano	Cohort	1095	1095	660	435	1.517241
50	Zijin Chen	Cohort	250	250	156	94	1.659575
51	Nada Dimkovic	Cohort	603	603			
52	Ling Sun	Cohort	159	159	51	108	0.4722222
53	Angelo Karaboyas	Cohort	4604	4604	2762	1842	1.499457
54	Ko-Lin Kuo	Cohort		42 230	20851	21379	0.9753029
55	Nadiesda A. Costa	Cohort	36450	36450	22415	14035	1.597079
56	Kunitoshi Iseki	Cohort	1525	1525	769	756	1.017196
57	Vincenzo Panichi	Cohort	753	753	457	296	1.543919
58	Shu-Ching Yeh	Cohort	1346	1346	767	579	1.324698
59	Xavier Cuevas	Cohort	2310	2310			
60	Yukio Maruyama	Cohort	149308	149308	92116	57192	1.610645
61	Andreas Schneider	RCTs	1015	1015	548	467	1.173447
62	Marisa Roldao	Cohort	59	59	37	22	1.681818
63	Hideki Fujii	Cohort	3312	3312	2110	1202	1.755408
64	Hyang Yun Lee	Cohort	123	123	65	58	1.12069

65	Shizuka Kobayashi	Cohort	175	175	122	53	2.301887
66	Anuja Shah	Cohort	2402	2402	1297	1105	1.173756
67	J. Bahlmann	RCTs	129	129	55	74	0.7432432
68	Victor E Pollak	Cohort	1774	1774	944	830	1.137349

Table 8. Average age, average length of the follow-up period, average body mass index, country and location of the study and reference group in each of the studies included in the analysis

Number	First authors	Country	Continent	Age	Follow up month	BMI	Reference group
1	Tetsuya Fujikawa	Japan	Asia	62.7	27.45	21	Base dose
2	Jiacong Luo	US	America	60.9	21	-	Not receiving EPO
3	Chang-Chyi Jenq	Taiwan	Asia	60.2	12	23.2	Base dose
4	Toshihide Hayashi	Japan	Asia	66	37.2	-	Base dose
5	Sai Pan	China	Asia	60.4	12	22.5	Base dose
6	Shunji Shiohira	Japan	Asia	66.8	36	22	Base dose
7	Tetsuya Ogawa	Japan	Asia	62.52	70.4	-	Base dose
8	Ouhong Wang	US	America	60.4	12	27	Base dose
9	Paulo Roberto SANTOS	Brazil	America	44.5	12	-	Base dose
10	Joan Fort	Spanish	Europe		24	-	Not receiving EPO
11	Uyen Duong	US	America	62	22.83	26.7	Base dose
12	Valeria Saglimbene	Italy	Europe	65.9	12	-	Base dose
13	Andreas Schneider	German	Europe	65.85	48	27.55	Base dose
14	Owen Kwon	Korea	Asia	59.6	19.4	22.4	Base dose
15	Rafael Perez-Garcia	Spanish	Europe	68.23	27.7	27.02	Base dose
16	Junichi Ishigami	Japan	Asia	61.46	24	-	Base dose
17	Joanne H. Lau	Canada	America	65.7	72	-	Base dose
18	Kenichi Tanaka	Japan	Asia	67	55.2	21.4	Base dose
19	Rieko Eriguchi	Japan	Asia	64.13	48	20.96	Base dose
20	Angie Nishio	US	America	62.1	30	-	Base dose
21	Xiangxue Lu	China	Asia	58.37	55	-	Base dose
22	Yi Zhang	US	America	75.65	9	-	Base dose
23	Dennis J. Cotter	US	America	64.4	12	-	Base dose
24	Wei Yang	US	America	63	22.7	-	Base dose
25	Brian D. Bradbury	US	America	60.3	12	26.97	Base dose
26	Yi Zhang	US	America	75.7	9	-	Base dose
27	Elani Streja	US	America	60	3	-	Base dose
28	Masayuki Okazaki	Japan	Asia	64.8	24	-	Base dose

29	Elani Streja	US	America	62	60	26.6	Base dose
30	Shingo Fukuma	Japan	Asia	64.3	12	-	Base dose
31	Marit M Suttorp	Netherland	Europe	64.42	60	-	Base dose
32	Huan-Cheng Chang	Taiwan	Asia	58.64	46.08	-	Not receiving EPO
33	Brian D. Bradbury	US	America	59.3	6	27.5	Base dose
34	M. Alan Brookhart	US	America	62.5	12	27.8	Base dose
35	J. Möcks	German	Europe	51.4	12	22.3	Not receiving EPO
36	Deborah L. Regidor	US	America	59.5	24	26.3	Not receiving EPO
37	Takahiro Yajima	Japan	Asia	63.4	55.2	22.2	Base dose
38	Joseph M. Messana	US	America	64.3	-	27.6	Not receiving EPO
39	Eric D. Weinhandl	US	America	63.2	36	-	Not receiving EPO
40	Alexander Kainz	Austrian	Europe	64.79	48	25.74	Base dose
41	Myoung Nam Bae	Korea	Asia	58	40		Base dose
42	Vincenzo Panichi	Italy	Europe	65.7	36	24	Not receiving EPO
43	HAROLD I. FELDMAN	US	America	52.88	6	-	Not receiving EPO
44	Scott Sibbel	US	America	62.2	12	-	Base dose
45	Ryan D. Kilpatrick	US	America	65	12	-	Base dose
46	Masayuki Okazaki	Japan	Asia	66	34.6	22	Base dose
47	Ben C. Wong	Canada	America	65	3	-	Base dose
48	Javier Varas	Spanish	Europe	69.31	17.79	26.4	Base dose
49	Takahiro Kuragano	Japan	Asia	61.8	24	-	Base dose
50	Zijin Chen	China	Asia	56.63	36	-	Base dose
51	Nada Dimkovic	Serbia	Europe		12	-	Base dose
52	Ling Sun	China	Asia	52.11	24	22.27	Base dose
53	Angelo Karaboyas	21 countries	international	64.1	8	28.1	Base dose
54	Ko-Lin Kuo	Taiwan	Asia	61.55	41	-	Base dose
55	Nadiesda A. Costa	US	America	46.8	6	-	Base dose
56	Kunitoshi Iseki	Japan	Asia	63.5	36	20.8	Base dose

57	Vincenzo Panichi	Italy	Europe	65.7	84	24	Base dose
58	Shu-Ching Yeh	Taiwan	Asia	56.2	37	-	Base dose
59	Xavier Cuevas	Spanish	Europe		24	-	Not receiving EPO
60	Yukio Maruyama	Japan	Asia	67.6	12	22.3	Base dose
61	Andreas Schneider	German	Europe	66	48	-	Base dose
62	Marisa Roldao	Portugal	Europe	74.58	3	-	Base dose
63	Hideki Fujii	Japan	Asia	65.5	24	-	Base dose
64	Hyang Yun Lee	Korea	Asia	68	24	24	Base dose
65	Shizuka Kobayashi	Japan	Asia	68.13	24	-	Base dose
66	Anuja Shah	US	America	58	26.26	-	Base dose
67	J. Bahlmann	German	Europe	57	6	-	Not receiving EPO
68	Victor E Pollak	US	America	59	6	-	Base dose

Table 9. Effect size and computational scales (log of effect size and corresponding confidence interval, standard error of effect size, weight assigned to each study) for studies included in the analysis

Number	First authors	Effect size	Lower limit	Upper limit	log Effect size	log LLCI	log ULCI	PP	selog Effect size	Weight
1	Tetsuya Fujikawa	2.33	1.33	4.07	0.845868	0.285179	1.403643	0.557775	0.284579	0.312968
2	Jiacong Luo	1.64	1.39	1.94	0.494696	0.329304	0.662688	0.167992	0.08571	1.8827
3	Chang-Chyi Jenq	1.014	1.002	1.026	0.013903	0.001998	0.025668	0.011765	0.006003	3.749691
4	Toshihide Hayashi	2.25	1.25	4.06	0.81093	0.223144	1.401183	0.590253	0.301149	0.28198
5	Sai Pan	1.62	1.26	2.08	0.482426	0.231112	0.732368	0.249942	0.127521	1.171385
6	Shunji Shiohira	3.64	2.03	6.28	1.291984	0.708036	1.83737	0.545386	0.278258	0.326103
7	Tetsuya Ogawa	1.86	1.25	2.75	0.620577	0.223144	1.011601	0.391025	0.199502	0.586411
8	Ouhong Wang	1.18	1.02	1.36	0.165514	0.019803	0.307485	0.14197	0.072434	2.196858
9	Paulo Roberto SANTOS	5.172	1.663	16.081	1.643259	0.508623	2.777638	1.134379	0.578765	0.080751
10	Joan Fort	0.76	0.64	0.9	-0.27444	-0.44629	-0.10536	0.169076	0.086263	1.870575
11	Uyen Duong	1.56	1.09	2.22	0.444686	0.086178	0.797507	0.352821	0.180011	0.695568
12	Valeria Saglimbene	0.98	0.64	1.52	-0.0202	-0.44629	0.41871	0.438913	0.223935	0.480868
13	Andreas Schneider	1.25	1.18	1.32	0.223144	0.165514	0.277632	0.054488	0.0278	3.408959
14	Owen Kwon	1.81	1.1	2.98	0.593327	0.09531	1.091923	0.498597	0.254386	0.383656
15	Rafael Perez-Garcia	1.47	1.11	1.94	0.385262	0.10436	0.662688	0.277426	0.141544	1.009912
16	Junichi Ishigami	2.73	1.2	6.24	1.004302	0.182322	1.83098	0.826679	0.421775	0.149229
17	Joanne H. Lau	1.03	1	1.05	0.029559	0	0.04879	0.019231	0.009812	3.719296
18	Kenichi Tanaka	2.57	1.05	6.27	0.943906	0.04879	1.835776	0.89187	0.455036	0.128929
19	Rieko Eriguchi	1.41	1.18	1.69	0.34359	0.165514	0.524729	0.181139	0.092418	1.741014
20	Angie Nishio	1.85	1.44	2.4	0.615186	0.364643	0.875469	0.260283	0.132798	1.106954
21	Xiangxue Lu	1.781	1.091	2.91	0.577175	0.087095	1.068153	0.490978	0.250499	0.394398
22	Yi Zhang	1.17	1.05	1.3	0.157004	0.04879	0.262364	0.105361	0.053755	2.703252
23	Dennis J. Cotter	1.67	1.35	2.06	0.512824	0.300105	0.722706	0.209882	0.107083	1.470109

24	Wei Yang	0.98	0.89	1.08	-0.0202	-0.11653	0.076961	0.097164	0.049573	2.822533
25	Brian D. Bradbury	0.93	0.92	0.95	-0.07257	-0.08338	-0.05129	0.021277	0.010856	3.70853
26	Yi Zhang	1.01	0.87	1.17	0.00995	-0.13926	0.157004	0.147053	0.075027	2.132055
27	Elani Streja	1.59	1.54	1.65	0.463734	0.431782	0.500775	0.037041	0.018899	3.593165
28	Masayuki Okazaki	4.204	1.173	15.065	1.436036	0.159565	2.712374	1.276338	0.651193	0.064076
29	Elani Streja	1.2	1.05	1.37	0.182322	0.04879	0.314811	0.132489	0.067597	2.321855
30	Shingo Fukuma	1.56	1.22	1.99	0.444686	0.198851	0.688135	0.243449	0.124209	1.214297
31	Marit M Suttorp	1.27	1.08	1.49	0.239017	0.076961	0.398776	0.159759	0.08151	1.977292
32	Huan-Cheng Chang	2.07	1.58	2.63	0.727549	0.457425	0.966984	0.239435	0.122161	1.241819
33	Brian D. Bradbury	0.9	0.79	1.02	-0.10536	-0.23572	0.019803	0.125163	0.063859	2.421809
34	M. Alan Brookhart	0.96	0.95	0.98	-0.04082	-0.05129	-0.0202	0.020619	0.01052	3.712105
35	J. Möcks	0.81	0.51	1.37	-0.21072	-0.67334	0.314811	0.525532	0.268129	0.348884
36	Deborah L. Regidor	1.23	1.14	1.33	0.207014	0.131028	0.285179	0.078165	0.03988	3.096722
37	Takahiro Yajima	1.06	1.03	1.08	0.058269	0.029559	0.076961	0.018692	0.009537	3.721962
38	Joseph M. Messana	1.43	1.25	1.63	0.357674	0.223144	0.48858	0.130906	0.066789	2.343226
39	Eric D. Weinhandl	1.07	0.96	1.18	0.067659	-0.04082	0.165514	0.097856	0.049926	2.812444
40	Alexander Kainz	2	1.47	2.72	0.693147	0.385262	1.000632	0.307485	0.15688	0.865232
41	Myoung Nam Bae	1.72	1.1	2.68	0.542324	0.09531	0.985817	0.443493	0.226272	0.472227
42	Vincenzo Panichi	1.62	1.18	2.23	0.482426	0.165514	0.802002	0.319576	0.163049	0.814892
43	HAROLD I. FELDMAN	1.02	0.86	1.22	0.019803	-0.15082	0.198851	0.179048	0.091351	1.762777
44	Scott Sibbel	0.94	0.76	1.18	-0.06188	-0.27444	0.165514	0.22739	0.116015	1.329229
45	Ryan D. Kilpatrick	0.69	0.47	1.01	-0.37106	-0.75502	0.00995	0.381014	0.194395	0.612555
46	Masayuki Okazaki	1.9	0.92	3.93	0.641854	-0.08338	1.368639	0.726786	0.370809	0.190849
47	Ben C. Wong	1.6	0.76	3.61	0.470004	-0.27444	1.283708	0.813704	0.415155	0.15383

48	Javier Varas	1.97	0.75	5.14	0.678034	-0.28768	1.637053	0.95902	0.489296	0.112024
49	Takahiro Kuragano	1.71	0.48	6.07	0.536493	-0.73397	1.803359	1.266865	0.64636	0.065021
50	Zijin Chen	2.22	1.18	4.17	0.797507	0.165514	1.427916	0.630409	0.321637	0.249504
51	Nada Dimkovic	1.225	0.704	2.129	0.202941	-0.35098	0.755652	0.552712	0.281996	0.318241
52	Ling Sun	1.112	1.029	1.202	0.10616	0.028588	0.183987	0.077827	0.039708	3.101492
53	Angelo Karaboyas	1.06	0.88	1.29	0.058269	-0.12783	0.254642	0.196373	0.100191	1.590992
54	Ko-Lin Kuo	0.99	0.94	1.05	-0.01005	-0.06188	0.04879	0.058841	0.030021	3.355821
55	Nadiesda A. Costa	1.89	1.67	2.15	0.636577	0.512824	0.765468	0.128891	0.065761	2.370605
56	Kunitoshi Iseki	0.899	0.49	1.648	-0.10647	-0.71335	0.499562	0.606035	0.309201	0.268518
57	Vincenzo Panichi	1.01	1.006	1.025	0.00995	0.005982	0.024693	0.014742	0.007522	3.73927
58	Shu-Ching Yeh	0.76	0.35	1.65	-0.27444	-1.04982	0.500775	0.775212	0.395516	0.168784
59	Xavier Cuevas	1.15	0.98	1.36	0.139762	-0.0202	0.307485	0.167723	0.085573	1.885719
60	Yukio Maruyama	1.025	1.021	1.029	0.024693	0.020783	0.028588	0.003895	0.001987	3.766081
61	Andreas Schneider	1.77	1.23	2.54	0.57098	0.207014	0.932164	0.361185	0.184278	0.669385
62	Marisa Roldao	5.4	1.31	22.32	1.686399	0.270027	3.105483	1.419084	0.724023	0.052002
63	Hideki Fujii	1.42	1.1	1.84	0.350657	0.09531	0.609766	0.259109	0.132198	1.114038
64	Hyang Yun Lee	4.4	1.2	16.1	1.481605	0.182322	2.778819	1.297215	0.661844	0.062064
65	Shizuka Kobayashi	5.51	1.71	17.78	1.706565	0.536493	2.878074	1.17151	0.597709	0.075815
66	Anuja Shah	0.74	0.59	0.91	-0.30111	-0.52763	-0.09431	0.206794	0.105507	1.496771
67	J. Bahlmann	1.05	0.74	14.89	0.04879	-0.30111	2.70069	2.6519	1.35301	0.015039
68	Victor E Pollak	1.41	1.19	1.66	0.34359	0.173953	0.506818	0.163228	0.08328	1.936885

Table 10. PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Page 1
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Page 2,3
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Page 4, 5
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Page 5
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Page 6
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	Page 5
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Page 6
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 6
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 6
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	Page 6
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	Page 6
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	Page 7
Effect	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Page 7

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
measures			
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	Page 6
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	Page 7,8
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Page 7, 8
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	Page 7,8
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	Page 7,8
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Page 7,8
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	Page 7,8
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	Page 7,8
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	Page 8,9
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	Page 8
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	Page 8,9
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Page 19,20
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	Page 10, 11, 12
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	Page 21-24
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Page 21, 24-26
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	Page 22,

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
			23, 24
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	Page 22, 23, 24
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Page 17
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Page 26-28
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Page 30
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Page 30
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Page 30
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	Page 31
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	Page 31
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	Page 31
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	Page 31
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	Page 31
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Page 30

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

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